

Database:

APA PsycInfo <1806 to November Week 5 2021>

#	Query	Results from 14 Dec 2021
1	laminectomy.mp.	271
2	(dissectom* or diskectom*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	105
3	(surg* adj3 decompression*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	339
4	(spin* adj3 fusion*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	163
5	neurosurgery.mp. or exp Neurosurgery/	18,686
6	(neurosurgical adj3 procedure*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,281
7	orthop?edic*.mp.	3,358
8	(spin* adj3 surg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	503
9	(back adj3 pain).mp. or exp Back Pain/ or (low adj3 back adj3 pain).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	7,103
10	radicul*.mp.	638
11	(spin* adj3 disease*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,024
12	exp Spinal Column/ or (spin* adj3 column*).mp. or spine.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	6,835
13	(lumbar adj3 vertebra*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key	660

	concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
14	9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13	14,889
15	((spine* or spinal* or lumbar*) adj7 (surg* or neurosurg* or orthop?ed*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,171
16	telemedicine*.mp. or exp Telemedicine/ or telehealth*.mp. or tele-health*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	12,667
17	exp Telephone Systems/ or telephone*.mp. or (cell adj3 phone*).mp. or mobile phone*.mp. or exp Mobile Phones/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	37,376
18	exp Smartphones/ or smartphone*.mp. or smart-phone*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	6,125
19	exp Tablet Computers/ or tablet*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	5,654
20	exp Mobile Applications/ or (mobile adj3 application*).mp.	3,420
21	(tele-rehabilitation* or telerehabilitation* or (tele adj3 rehabilitation*)).mp. or exp Telerehabilitation/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	304
22	telenurs*.mp.	114
23	((video adj3 conf*) or video-conf* or videoconf*).mp. or exp Videoconferencing/	2,839
24	((health adj3 communica*) or (medic* adj3 inform*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	13,247
25	exp "Information and Communication Technology"/ or (informat* adj3 communicat* adj3 techn*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading	191,536

	word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
26	(informatic* adj3 application*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	165
27	exp Health Information Technology/ or (health adj3 informat* adj3 techn*).mp. or (nurs* adj3 inform*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	7,835
28	(exp Electronic Health Services/ or (electronic adj3 health adj3 service*).mp. or ehealth.mp. or e-health.mp.) adj5 (communicat*.mp. or exp Interpersonal Communication/) [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,749
29	((home adj3 visit*) or (house adj3 call*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	6,203
30	(real-time adj3 support*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	189
31	exp Aftercare/ or (after adj3 car*).mp. or after-car*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	10,299
32	((followup adj3 car*) or (follow-up adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,926
33	((followup adj3 support*) or (follow-up adj3 support*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	1,126
34	(remote adj3 monitor*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	322
35	(active adj3 post-discharge adj3 surveillanc*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading	0

	word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	
36	exp Simulation/ or simulation*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	102,505
37	((instruction* adj3 film*) or (instruction* adj3 video*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,376
38	(pain adj3 manag*).mp. or exp Pain Management/	17,149
39	analgesia*.mp. or exp Analgesia/	8,890
40	(clinic* adj3 teach* adj3 method*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	116
41	(client* adj3 educat*).mp. or exp Client Education/ or (patient* adj3 educat*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	20,778
42	((patient* adj3 car*) or (car* adj3 behavior*)).mp. or exp Caring Behaviors/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	94,736
43	self-car*.mp. or exp Self-Care/ or (self adj3 car*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	27,118
44	(health adj3 promot*).mp. or exp Health Promotion/	50,575
45	((multi-discliplin* adj3 car*) or (multidisciplin adj3 car*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	0
46	(self-manag* or (self adj3 manag*)).mp. or exp Self-Management/ [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	17,814

47	recover*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	93,451
48	exp Rehabilitation/ or rehab*.mp. or convalescence.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	90,030
49	(mobile adj3 team\$).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	253
50	exp Text Messaging/ or (text adj3 messag*).mp.	3,455
51	((pre-operative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 educat*) or (preoperative adj3 exercise*) or (pre-operative adj3 exercise*) or prehabilitation).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	156
52	(emotional adj3 adjust*).mp. or exp Emotional Adjustment/ or (psychologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 psychologic*).mp. or (physiologic* adj3 adjust*).mp. or (adapt* adj3 physiologic*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	78,781
53	(adaptive adj3 behavior*).mp. or exp Adaptive Behavior/	13,450
54	((short adj3 time adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 term adj3 stay*) or (short adj3 time adj3 hospitalization*) or (short adj3 term adj3 hospitalization*)).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	291
55	(return* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,498
56	(hospital* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,959
57	exp Hospital Discharge/ or discharg*.mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	40,105

58	(postdischarg* or (post adj3 discharg*) or postdischarg*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	2,745
59	(transition* adj3 home*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	949
60	(length* adj3 stay*).mp. [mp=title, abstract, heading word, table of contents, key concepts, original title, tests & measures, mesh word]	10,503
61	1 or 2 or 3 or 4	813
62	5 or 6 or 7 or 8	23,171
63	14 and 62	769
64	15 or 61 or 63	2,104
65	54 or 55 or 56 or 57 or 58 or 59 or 60	53,060
66	16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27 or 28 or 29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41 or 42 or 43 or 44 or 45 or 46 or 47 or 48 or 49 or 50 or 51 or 52 or 53	750,326
67	64 and 65 and 66	55
68	limit 67 to (danish or english or norwegian or swedish)	54